

National Leprosy Conference 2025

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Abstract Book

OP -3: Strengthening Supervision of Leprosy Prevention and Control Activities in Colombo Regional Director of Health Services Area

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Background

Regular, standard supervision is an essential part of effective prevention and control of leprosy. Formal supervisions with documented feedback on strengths, areas requiring improvement and recommendations are crucial for continued improvement. Structured supervision report formats ensure that all relevant aspects are addressed during a supervision, are documented and communicated. They also serve as evidence of district level supervisory activities and inform the National level.

Description of the intervention/initiative

A comprehensive supervision tool to assess all domains of leprosy prevention and control at Medical Officer of Health (MOH) level was developed with the expert inputs including that of Anti Leprosy Campaign. Aspects that need to be covered including logistics, service delivery, surveillance activities and compliance with national and district level initiatives were identified with the involvement of MOH staff as well. The tool comprised nine sections which focused on general information, documentation at MOH office (spot map, availability of registers), individual patient data-tallied with notification registers and the national database, case surveillance and reporting, contact tracing and management, health education and awareness activities, staff capacity and training, community engagement and challenges and remarks and recommendations.

Methods used for the evaluation

The tool was utilized in leprosy-focused MOH supervisions by the district team. Its feasibility in administration, ability to capture all relevant data and overall efficiency was assessed. The concurrence of the National team was sought in finalizing the tool.

Results

The supervision tool helped to streamline district level supervisory activities. It facilitated a structured evaluation of MOH level activities where all relevant areas were addressed and assessed efficiently. The tool was sensitive to identify discrepancies in individual level data. The efforts of the district team were made efficient. Feedback from MOH staff revealed improved quality of supervision. Completed supervision reports were submitted to the national level through the recommended channels.

Lessons learnt

The introduction of a structured standard supervision tool to evaluate leprosy prevention and control activities is both an effective and efficient.